

Improved Dynamic Response of PV and Battery Based Dynamic System

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Abstract— The idea behind a smart grid is to "digitally upgrade" distribution and long-distance transmission grids in order to improve present operations by cutting losses and to create new markets for the generation of alternative energy sources. A PV cell's material science is similar to that of a conventional p-n intersecting diode. To increase the main grid's dependability, the PV-based system might be connected there as supplemental power. However, the substantial dynamic interactions that can result from the converter-based PV system's link to the main grid could result in a variety of unstable problems. The project deals DC micro-grid buck boost converter with existing method compared to proposed DC micro-grid SEPIC converter system in MATLAB Simulink. A DC micro grid system has been proposed as a SEPIC converter power network that enables the introduction of a large amount of solar energy using distributed photovoltaic and battery units source side input. The voltage flow adjustment in the DC micro grid system. This work deals with modeling and simulation of DC micro -grid system with PI, FOPID and FL controllers. The performance of DC micro grid system based SEPIC and buck boost controller with PI, FOPID and FLC are compared and their results are presented. The results indicate that FLC controlled SEPIC converter gives superior response.

Keywords—SEPIC, Buck Boost, Solar panel, FOPID, Controllers

I. INTRODUCTION

In the present era, due to increased power demand to meet up the industrial requirements, the shortfalls in power generation have been attempted to mitigate between supply and demand through developments of National Grid connected systems connected on the basis of the zonal requirement, the energy management is implemented. An "electricity grid" is not a single entity but an aggregate of multiple networks and multiple power generation companies with multiple operators employing varying levels of communication and coordination, most of which is manually controlled. The contrasts with 60 percent efficiency for grids based on the latest technology may be the solution for the above problem.

A micro grid is an umbrella term that covers modernization of both the transmission and distribution grids. The concept of a smart grid is that of a 'digital upgrade' of distribution and long-distance transmission grids to both optimize current operations by reducing the losses, as well as open up new markets for alternative energy production. A Future Grid is an electricity network that can intelligently integrate the actions of devices connected to it. In the order to efficiently deliver sustainable, economic and secure electricity supplies, it employs innovative products and services together with intelligent monitoring, control, communication, and self-healing technologies to better facilities the connection and operation of generators of all sizes and technologies, allow consumers to play a part in optimizing the operation of the system, provide consumers with greater information and choice of supply, significantly reduce the environmental impact of the whole electricity supply system and deliver enhanced levels of reliability and security of supply. This

include the ability to reduce power consumption at the consumer side during peak hours, called Demand side management; enabling grid connection of distributed generation power incorporating grid energy storage for distributed generation load balancing; and eliminating failures such as widespread power grid cascading failures. The increased efficiency and reliability of the smart grid is expected to save consumers money and help reduce CO₂ emissions. Governments increasingly focus on energy security, investing in the Smart Grid could be used to reduce dependence on non-domestic energy sources. It could also make the grid more resistant to military or terrorist attacks, by physical or digital means micro grid is referred to by other names including 'Micro Electric Grid', 'Micro Power Grid' and 'Future Grid'. This project offers a constant output voltage and it can be controlled by different combinations of external source. It shows no ripples in the output and gives a constant stable voltage power and current. This can be used in speed control of DC motor, control of servo motor and battery charging

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section presents the contribution towards researchers in this context.

"A Voltage-Balancer-Based Cascaded DC-DC Converter with a Novel Power Feedforward Control for the Medium-Voltage DC Grid Interface of Photovoltaic Systems." by Zhuang, Y. et al. A novel power feedforward voltage-balancing control strategy is used to create a multi-port cascaded DC-DC converter based on a voltage balancer (VB). The converter has a MVDC grid-connected output terminal and multiple PV array input terminals. The VB regulates the differential power from one SM to another, ensuring that the SM output voltages are equal. The proposed converter appears to have excellent dynamic performance and voltage-balancing capacity, according to both simulation and experimental findings.

"Design and Simulation of a Boost-Micro inverter for Optimized Photovoltaic System Performance." Shahd Fadhil Jaber et al provide a performance comparison between particle swarm optimization (PSO) and perturbation and observation (P&O) algorithms for obtaining MPP for the PV system. At the point when the irradiance changes, the miniature inverter adjusts under halfway circumstances. The miniature inverter is planned by MATLAB/Simulink/2020a programming. The PV produces an alternating current [Ac] output voltage of 110 V rms at its maximum input voltage of 80 V DC. When the P&O algorithm is used, the output voltage and current total harmonic distortion (THD) ratios are 2.58% and 2.76 percent, respectively. When the PSO algorithm is used, the ratios are 2.45% and 2.58%. The PV framework

productivity accomplished by utilizing P&O, PSO are 95.7%, 96.8%.

"Analysis and Control of a Novel Transformer-Less Micro inverter for PV-Grid Interface" by M. Rajeev discusses how a proportional resonant (PR) controller's dynamic model was derived from the topology through the use of small-signal analysis. The PR controller's optimal proportional and integral gains are designed using a step-by-step approach that takes into account the effects of pulse width modulation transport and digital sampling delays. Experiments conducted in a 200 W laboratory back up theoretical claims and simulation outcomes.

"A novel high step-up DC-DC converter based on three-winding coupled inductor" by M. Khalilzadeh et al. The idea is for a novel boost DC/DC converter. The voltage gain goes up as a result of the three-winding coupled inductor that is present in the proposed topology. One more benefit of recommended geography is that by diminishing the turn's proportion of the coupled inductor the voltage gain of converter is expanded. A passive clamp circuit is used in the proposed converter to recover the stored energy in the leakage inductance. Additionally, voltage stress on the main switch is reduced in the proposed topology. Consequently, power losses are reduced when a power switch with lower resistance RDS (ON) and fewer winding turns are used.

"Overview on hybrid solar photovoltaic-electrical energy storage technologies for power supply to buildings." by Jia Liu, Xi Chen et al primarily addresses hybrid photovoltaic-electrical energy storage systems for building power generation and supply and provides a comprehensive summary of authorized report findings and academic research outputs from literatures. First, we look at the global installation capacity of hybrid photovoltaic-electrical energy storage systems to see how much progress has been made in emerging markets. This study gives a knowledge of the momentum advancement, research degree and plan improvement of cross breed photovoltaic-electrical energy stockpiling frameworks for power supply to structures and can act as an express aide for additional examination in the connected region.

"Improved Hybrid Switched Inductor/Switched Capacitor DC-DC Converters" by B. Faridpak, et al The proposed structures have a lower duty cycle ratio and a higher voltage gain than the conventional structures, which are either switched inductor-based or switched capacitor-based. The efficiency is improved, particularly for high voltage gains, by including an auxiliary switch. The guideline of activity and consistent state examination are talked about exhaustively. Additionally, an experimentally constructed prototype serves as a validation for the simulation results generated by PSCAD/EMTDC software.

The outcomes showed the way that the voltage gain and proficiency could be improved by using the assistant switch.

III. BIDIRECTIONAL BUCK/BOOST CONVERTER

The PV-based system can be connected to the main grid nearby as supplementary power to improve the reliability of the main grid. However, the extensive interconnection of the converter-based PV system to the main grid can lead to lots of dynamic interactions and may cause different kinds of unstable issues. The PV system can also operate in standalone mode for local applications in remote non-electrified regions, such as in the desert, on mountains, etc. Constructing small-scale standalone PV-based system which can power the surrounding loads in those regions is much more cost-effective than extending the conventional main grid to those areas. The PV-based standalone micro grid is thus proposed to realize this kind of application, which has also gained growing attraction in recent years.

The micro grid (or mini grid) can integrate the PV panels, energy storage devices, and controllable loads electively and economically. By taking some reasonable control measures, the micro grid can implement the optimal use of energy. In practice, this system can be divided into two types: DC micro grid and AC micro grid. The former is widely used in modern applications which is because of the inherent advantages of DC micro grids, such as that the control is simple, no need for synchronization, no reactive power, no low frequency harmonics and excellent compatibility with sources, storage devices and loads, etc.

The PV panels power the DC load on the DC bus via a boost converter and the battery is connected to the DC bus through a bidirectional buck/boost converter. The boost converter regulates the power of the PV panels, while the bidirectional buck/boost converter controls the charging and discharging procedures of the battery. When the maximum power of the PV panels is insufficient for the load, then the PV panels operate in MPPT mode and the battery provides the complementary power to the load, which also needs to control the bus voltage. If the power of the PV panels becomes larger than the load, the excessive power will be provided to the battery. Under this condition, if the charge current or charge voltage of the battery achieves the maximum value recommended by the manufacturers, the charging procedure of the battery requires to be controlled.

Fig 3.1 Circuit Diagram of Existing System

Meanwhile, the PV panels need to quit MPPT control and start to take care of the DC bus voltage. Therefore, according to the power supplied by the PV panels, the battery states and the load conditions, the PV based DC Micro grid is able to operate in multiple operating modes, as given below. Here, P_m is the maximum output power of the PV panels, P_o is the load requirement power, v_{bat} and i_{bat} are the battery voltage and current, respectively. I_{bmax} is the recommended maximum charge current for the battery, while V_{bmin} and V_{bmax} are the allowed minimum and maximum battery voltage, respectively.

Operating Mode Description: M1—when $P_m < P_o$, the solar power is insufficient, the PV panels are thus operating in MPPT mode controlled by the boost converter, while the battery supplies the complementary power via the bidirectional buck/boost converter working in boost mode to regulate the DC bus voltage v_o , the inductor current i_{Lb2} is positive. In Fig 3.1 shows the energy flow and the corresponding control requirements of M1, in which d_1 and d_2 are the duty cycles of Q1 and Q2, respectively, Q3 is always complementary to Q2. When $P_m > P_o$, the excessive power will be stored in the battery. Under this condition, if $i_{bat} < I_{bmax}$, it is unnecessary to control i_{bat} , so the control system is the same as that in Fig 3.1

M2—when $P_m > P_o$ and i_{bat} reaches the maximum charge current limit I_{bmax} , i_{bat} is required to be controlled so as to protect the battery. Thus, the bidirectional buck/boost converter operates in buck mode to control i_{bat} . Meanwhile, the PV panels have to quit MPPT control mode and to regulate the dc bus voltage, as shown in Fig 3.1

M3—when $P_m > P_o$ and v_{bat} achieves the maximum battery voltage limit V_{bmax} , the bidirectional converter will operate in buck mode to control v_{bat} . At the same time, the boost converter still regulates v_o , as shown in Fig 3.1

IV SEPIC CONVERTER

The Single-Ended Primary-Inductor Converter, SEPIC, can be described as a boost converter followed by a buck-boost converter, see Fig 2.5(i). The converter consists of two inductors, one switch, one diode, one coupling capacitor and one output capacitor. The voltage over the coupling capacitor, C_p , will be an average voltage of V_{in} and with a large capacitor it will be close to constant. C_p prevents any DC current from owing between the high- and low-voltage side and it also enables the output voltage to be lower than the input voltage. Without C_p , the diode would be forward biased and nothing would prevent a current owing from V_{in} to V_{out} when $V_{in} > V_{out}$. The diode needs to be connected to a known potential; this is accomplished with the second inductance, L_2 , which connects the diode to ground.

Fig 4.1 Circuit Diagram of SEPIC Converter

In the first phase, during on-time, the inductance L_1 has a constant voltage of V_{in} applied and energy is stored in the inductor, see Fig 2.5(ii)(a). Since the high- voltage side of C_p is connected to ground via the conducting switch, the low-voltage side will be kept at V_{in} . The voltage over the second inductance, L_2 , which is connected between the low-voltage side of C_p and ground will be V_{in} . This makes the diode reverse biased and as a result, L_2 will be charged by C_p .

During the switch time, L_1 charged C_p and L_2 which are in parallel with the load, see Figure 2.5(ii)(b). The voltage over L_2 will then become equal V_{out} which makes the diode forward biased and conducting, L_2 then supplies energy to the load through the diode.

Modes of Operation: A SEPIC is said to be in continuous-conduction mode (“continuous mode”) if the current through the inductor L_1 never falls to zero. During a SEPIC’s steady-state operation, the average voltage across capacitor C_1 (V_{C1}) is equal to the input voltage (V_{in}). Because capacitor C_1 blocks direct current (DC), the average current through it (I_{C1}) is zero, making inductor L_2 the only source of DC load current. Therefore, the average current through inductor L_2 (I_{L2}) is the same as the average load current and hence independent of the input voltage.

Looking at average voltages, the following can be written:

$$V_{IN} = V_{L1} + V_{C1} + V_{L2}$$

Because the average voltage of V_{C1} is equal to V_{IN} , $V_{L1} = -V_{L2}$. For this reason, the two inductors can be wound on the same core. Since the voltages are the same in magnitude, their effects of the mutual inductance will be zero, assuming the polarity of the windings is correct. Also, since the voltages are the same in magnitude, the ripple currents from the two inductors will be equal in magnitude.

$$I_{D1} = I_{L1} - I_{L2}$$

The average currents can be summed as follows (average capacitor currents must be zero):

Fig 4.2 : With S1 closed current increases through L_1 (green) and C_1 discharges increasing current in L_2 (red)

When switch S_1 is turned off, the current I_{C1} becomes the same as the current I_{L1} , since inductors do not allow instantaneous changes in current. The current I_{L2} will continue in the negative direction, in fact it never reverses direction. It can be seen from the diagram that a negative I_{L2} will add to the current I_{L1} to increase the current delivered to the load. Using Kirchoff’s Current Law, it can be shown that $I_{D1} = I_{C1} - I_{L2}$. It can then be concluded, that while S_1 is off, power is delivered to the load from both L_2 and L_1 . C_1 , however is being charged by L_1 during this off cycle, and will in turn recharge L_2 during the on cycle.

Fig 4.3: With S1 Open Current Through L_1 (Green) And Current Through L_2 (Red) Produce Current Through The Load

Because the potential (voltage) across capacitor c_1 may reverse direction every cycle, a non-polarized capacitor should be used. However, a polarized tantalum or electrolytic capacitor may be used in some cases, because

the potential (voltage) across capacitor C1 will not change unless the switch is closed long enough for a half cycle of resonance with inductor L2, and by this time the current in inductor L1 could be quite large.

Discontinuous Mode: As discussed above, in CCM SEPIC has no line-frequency energy storage function and the output capacitance need be large to store the line frequency energy and suppress the low frequency voltage ripple for LED applications. Therefore, it is very difficult to eliminate the electrolytic capacitors in CCM SEPIC with low output voltage ripple, which is highly desirable for LED lighting application. For DCM operation of SEPIC, there are two types of DCM operation.

The first one is defined as the current of the output diode is in continuous current mode or not. When the output diode current is zero, the inductor L1 current and inductor L2 current are not zero and equal to each other. In this case, the middle capacitor still has no low frequency energy storage function since its low frequency voltage still follows the input voltage due to continuous current of inductor L1 and L2. For the second type of DCM operation, which the inductor L1 current and inductor L2 current will both reach zero in a switching period. After the inductor L1 current reaches zero, the voltage of middle capacitor will not follow input voltage anymore and will have the low frequency energy storage function. Therefore, for the second type of DCM SEPIC, by allowing a relative large voltage ripple across the middle capacitor, the capacitance value of middle capacitor and output capacitor could be largely reduced thus eliminating the electrolytic capacitors.

V MATLAB SIMULATION & RESULT

Electrical power systems are combinations of electrical circuits and electro-mechanical devices like motors and generators. Engineers working in this discipline are constantly improving the performance of the systems. Requirements for drastically increased efficiency have forced power system designers to use power electronic devices and sophisticated control system concepts that tax traditional analysis tools and techniques. Further complicating the analyst's role is the fact that the system is often so nonlinear that the only way to understand it is through simulation. Land-based power generation from hydroelectric, steam or other devices is not the only use of power systems. A common attribute of these systems is their use of power electronics and control systems to achieve their performance objectives. Sim Power Systems is a modern design tool that allows scientists and engineers to rapidly and easily build models that simulate power systems. Sim Power Systems uses the Simulink environment, allowing you to build a model using simple click and drag procedures. Not only can you draw the circuit topology rapidly, but your analysis of the circuit can

include its interactions with mechanical, thermal, control, and other disciplines. This is possible because all the electrical parts of the simulation interact with the extensive Simulink modeling library. Since Simulink uses MATLAB as its computational engine, designers can also use MATLAB toolboxes and Simulink block sets.

A PI controller with the transfer function

$$G_c(s) = K_p + K_i s \tag{1}$$

is employed to control the process. Hence,

$$G_c(j\omega) = K_p - jK_i \omega \tag{2}$$

With PI control it is possible to move the given point on the Nyquist curve in two direction in the complex plane, as is indicated in Fig. 1. The point A may be moved in the direction of ω by changing the gain and in the orthogonal direction by changing the integral gain. The degree range of the movement of the point A is from 0 to 90 degree

Fig 5.1: Simulation circuit of PI controller

Circuit diagram of SEPIC and buck boost converter with closed loop PI controller is delineated in Fig.3.25. Input voltage is delineated in Fig.3.26 & its value is 19V. Voltage across RL-load is delineated in Fig.3.27 & its value is 95V. Output current through RL load is delineated in Fig.3.28 & its value is 0.98A. Output power is delineated in Fig.3.29 & its value is 90W.

Input Voltage (Vi)

Output Voltage (Vo)

Output Current (Io)

Output Power Po

Fig 5.2: Results pf PI Controller

A proportional–integral–derivative controller (PID controller) is a generic control loop feedback mechanism(controller) widely used in industrial control systems. A PID controller calculates an “error” value as the difference between a measured process variable and a desired set point. The controller attempts to minimize the error by adjusting the process control inputs. The proportional integral derivative controller is used to improve the stability of the control system and to decrease steady state error.

Fig 5.3 Simulation Circuit of FOPID

The PID controller, transfer function is given by

$$U(s)/(E(s)) = K_p + K_i/s + K_d s$$

K_p is the proportionality constant
 K_i is the integral constant.
 K_d is the derivative constant.

Output Voltage

Output Current

Output Power

Fig 5.4 Simulation Results of FOPID

Circuit diagram of SEPIC and buck boost converter with closed loop FOPID controller is delineated in Fig. 5.4. Input voltage is its value is 19V. Voltage across RL-load is value is 97V. Output current through RL load is its value is 0.99A. Output power is delineated in ts value is 95W.

A solar photovoltaic generator connected to a DC-DC boost converter, perturb & observe and fuzzy logic based maximum power point tracking algorithm in the order to minimize the loss of energy provided by the PV module and to improve energy efficiency. Fuzzy controller consists of three important procedures, including fuzzification, fuzzy rule and defuzzification. The fuzzification converts the real variables to fuzzy variables through linguistic variables

Fig 5.5 Simulation Circuit of FLC

Circuit diagram of SEPIC and buck boost converter with closed loop FL controller is delineated in Fig. 5.5. Input voltage is delineated and its value is 19V. Voltage across RL-load is delineated in Fig. 3.39 and its value is 95V. Output current through RL load is delineated in Fig. 3.40 and its value is 0.98A. Output power is delineated in Fig. 3.41 and its value is 85W.

Fig 5.6 Simulation Result of FLC

VI CONCLUSION

Comparison of Buck boost converter and SEPIC converter in smart grid are simulated using Matlab simulink. Comparison is done in terms of output voltage and output power. By using SEPIC converter, output voltage is enhanced from 70V to 95V, output ripple voltage is reduced from 1.0V to 0.3V and output power is enhanced from 50W to 90W. The outcome represents that the output voltage and output power are enhanced using SEPIC converter. Hence, SEPIC converter in DC micro grid is superior to Buck boost converter in DC micro grid.

Closed loop SEPIC converter with PI and FLC controllers are simulated using Mat lab simulink. Comparison is done in terms of settling time and steady state error. By using FLC controller, the settling time is reduced from 0.50Sec to 0.06Sec and the steady state error is reduced from 1.8V to 0.5V. Both Settling time and steady state error are reduced using FLC controller. Hence, closed loop DC micro

grid based SEPIC converter with FLC controller is superior to closed loop DC micro grid based SEPIC converter with PI controller.

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